

ALL-Ready – The European Agroecology
Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: preparation phase

.....

AgroEcoLLNet Vision and mission document

.....

Authors: Muriel Mambrini-Doudet, Bastian Gödel, Anna Krzywoszynska, Chris McPhee

Deliverable Number	D1.3
Work Package	WP1
Deliverable type	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Deliverable leader	INRAE
Due date	31 August 2021
Submission date	May 2022
Version	V1
Contact	Muriel Mambrini-Doudet (muriel.mambrini@inrae.fr)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000349 (ALL-Ready).

History of changes

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
V0	November 2021	Muriel Mambrini-Doudet	N/A
V0.1-2-3	November 2021	WP1 contributors	Comments
V0.4	December 2021	All WP leaders	Comments
V1	May 2022	Muriel Mambrini-Doudet	Addition of Annex

Disclaimer

The information and views set out in this deliverable are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Table of Contents

INTRODUCTION	4
1. VISION OF THE NETWORK	5
2. MISSION OF THE NETWORK.....	5
ANNEX: TRANSLATION OF THE VISION AND MISSION	6
2.1 THE UNIQUE FEATURES OF THE FUTURE NETWORK	6
2.1.1 Network identity	6
2.1.2 The expertise.....	6
2.1.3 A network of networks	6
2.1.4 A space.....	7
2.1.5 Obvious benefits	7
2.2 SOME POINTS OF ATTENTION WHEN DESIGNING THE FUTURE NETWORK	7

List of abbreviations

CSA	Coordination and Support Action
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
LL	Living Lab
RI	Research Infrastructure
SCAR AE SWG	Standing Committee on Agricultural Research's Strategic Working Group on Agroecology
WP	Work Package

Introduction

ALL-Ready is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the European Commission (EC) with the aim of preparing a framework for a future European Network of Living Labs (LL) and Research Infrastructures (RI) that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe. Based on the premise that agroecology can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, the project will contribute to addressing the multiple challenges that they are facing today including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, degradation of soil and water quality.

This deliverable sets out the vision and the mission for the Network of LL and RI for an agroecology transition throughout Europe, that is being framed in ALL-Ready.

They have been defined building on the work achieved for D1.1 "Reference document with key concepts: Vision for building the network of living labs and research infrastructures for agroecology transition" and D1.2 "Definitions and a set of inclusion criteria for agroecology living labs, pertinent research infrastructures and their synergies", and the ideas collected during the project workshop held on 4 October 2021 which gathered consortium members and stakeholders in the domain.

The vision and the mission here are distinct from the ones being built for the Partnership on Agroecology, although they will be considered by the SCAR Strategic Working Group on Agroecology (SCAR-AE SWG) in order to be coherent.

A first draft has been agreed among the WP leaders of ALL-Ready in December 2021, presented at the 1st meeting of the pilot network in the same month for adjustments. It has then been revisited during the annual meeting of the ALL-Ready consortium in March 2022: a workshop was organised to project the ideal activities of the network. The synthesis of what has been outlined is in annex of the present deliverable.

1. Vision of the Network

Accelerate the transition to agroecology throughout Europe by connecting and empowering place-based innovation from 2023 onwards.

2. Mission of the Network

The Network connects RI, LL and other open innovation initiatives across Europe that support practices for agricultural production that pilot, create and use diversity. Organisations joining the Network identify themselves with a set of criteria: i) co-creation of knowledge and innovation; ii) promotion of resilience, sustainability and diversity; iii) support for climate change adaptation and mitigation, iv) synergies between ecosystem functions; v) promotion of efficiency and responsibility in the use of natural resources; vi) development of circular and solidarity economies, value given to social and ecological justice. The Network offers the possibility to upscale and out-scale local advances through productive synergies beyond cultural frontiers and to monitor progress across Europe. Its activities are appropriately supported by regional and national funders. The Network as a whole empowers the diversity of actors involved as knowledge-makers, produces a continuous science–policy dialogue, delivers evidence needed for a stronger alignment of the funding landscape with the needs for agroecological innovation, and enables the production of new and relevant transdisciplinary research questions to strengthen the field of agroecology. As a result, the Network supports inclusive place-based innovation that accelerates the transition to agroecology at the local, regional and national levels in every European country.

Annex: translation of the vision and mission

At the annual meeting organised the 6th and 7th March 2022, the ALL-Ready consortium members have been invited to translate the vision, mission and work on the indicators undertaken so far (see deliverable 1.2) to foresee the activities and particular role of the future network of LLs and RIs to facilitate the agroecology. The outcomes of the meeting are synthesised below.

2.1 The unique features of the future network

2.1.1 Network identity

The network assembles the actors concerned by primary production as agents of the acceleration of the agroecology transition through the development of LLs and their connections with RIs. It lies in a landscape of initiatives, is open to new perspectives and maintains links with organisations concerned by the food systems transition, soil health and environmental issues. In particular, whereas the network is one major component of the partnership for agroecology, it is connected to the food systems partnership and to the soil mission namely through the LLs and lighthouses foreseen to be implemented. More generally, specialised in LLs and in the connection between LLs and RIs, the network is meant to be recognised and connected to other LL and RI networks, at the local, European and international levels (ENoLL, ESFRI...).

2.1.2 The expertise

The network is specialised in the identification and support to the different forms of impacts linked to the agroecology transition (research, empowerment, economy, social), and in putting the farmer at the centre of the activities. It is ready to deal with the complexity, and able to value local achievements and advances at the more global level. This means that the network is adapted to welcome local initiatives and to confer capacities to scale up. The network is connected to other networks of the AKIS (agriculture knowledge and innovation systems) and has a particular link with EIP Agri.

2.1.3 A network of networks

It is a network of networks, gathering knowledge on and from:

- LLs and RIs
- Open innovation arrangements for the agroecology transition

Such organisations are not bound by one definition but are active according to principles orienting knowledge sharing and capacity building. Such principles are then translated depending on the local situation and innovation ecosystem. This means that:

- time is required to gain a common understanding amongst different actors;
- the network includes very diverse organisations, which are, in addition, operating at very different scales (local to international).

These organisations have in common the understanding of their role in the agroecology transition, they understand their distinctions and complementarities, thanks also to their agency in the network. They see themselves as being active members of the network.

This means that the network recognises very different ways of decision making and a diversity of governance structures.

2.1.4 A space

The network is a space where:

- Place-based research and transdisciplinarity are valued: a space offering a good capacity for dialogue between disciplines that hardly dialogue;
- Which has a capacity to transform research at a higher speed than in usual organisations, and where transdisciplinary capacities are reinforced and their rigor acknowledged;
- Possibilities are offered for collaboration for agroecology transition in Europe.

2.1.5 Obvious benefits

The members find:

- Capacity building through:
 - o sharing of experience (manuals, best practices, technical),
 - o intelligence gathering (collective learning processes, knowledge exchange capacities, experimentation);
- Matching and methods for matching, facilitated by research and researchers:
 - o Between a diversity of stakeholders,
 - o Between researchers and producers closer to market,
 - o Between the producers and the consumers;
- Ways to fund:
 - o By attracting private and public funding,
 - o By learning how to develop adequate business plans;
- Specific topics:
 - o Economic sustainability of agroecology transition,
 - o Development of landscape approaches,
 - o Production of specific indicators and tool boxes guaranteeing the rigor and the robustness of the knowledge produced while it is constantly evolving and needs to be open to regional adaptations:
 - A special attention regarding the indicators: they need to record and demonstrate the social outcomes of the LLs and RIs and their accelerating effects for agroecology transition,
 - A special attention regarding the knowledge, tools and theories that help to compare place-based studies;
- Links between LLs and RIs;
- Knowledge management and database:
 - o Gather the RIs that hold databases,
 - o Virtual Research Environment (VRE).

2.2 Some points of attention when designing the future network

ALL-Ready works on the components of an enabling environment and remain vigilant to:

- o Check soundness and link to realities and on-going initiatives,
- o Have a special attention to the attractiveness of the network and to incentives to be involved,
- o Provide rigorous frames to facilitate upscaling:
 - Policies,

- Research,
- Capacity building.

In order to do so, we identified some points requiring attention. We need not to forget to:

- ✓ Think about what the members can give to the network and the benefits from the network for each activity;
- ✓ Watch the language, to be translated in every country and for every actor;
- ✓ Always consider LLs AND RIs (and not solely LL);
- ✓ Be clear about:
 - The degree of transdisciplinarity handled by the future network,
 - The stability of the network (needs to be studied before the implementation and the way it will be achieved will serve in return the sustainability of the LLs and RIs)
- ✓ Ask for the inputs and points of views of the ones who will benefit from the network;
- ✓ Connect the network to other networks and more particularly to EIP Agri:
 - Look at what is done, in particular tips to ensure the participation,
 - Look at the outcomes of EIP Agri,
 - Examine the interest of building thematic clusters,
 - Bridge with other relevant pan-European initiatives in networking and joint programming (ERA-Nets, JPIs...);
- ✓ Stay cautious to always give value to the diversity, to go beyond the specificities and fight against the tendency to harmonise.